
Intellectual Property Rights and E-commerce

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14909834

Abstract:

Intellectual Property Rights Laws provide the protection to the inventor or creator for the protection of their intellectual property. It plays very important role for providing protection in the e-commerce business. E-commerce business is the online trading of goods and or services. In online business most of the business websites often breaks the intellectual property laws. There are so many parts which needs to follow for not infringes the intellectual property law that includes the creations must be own, permission should be taken from the creator for the use of their invention etc. In this research paper researcher has discussed the IPRs laws, significance of IP in e-commerce and elements of e-commerce like the business websites and their contents, databases etc. which should have been taken the permission of IPRs while doing business through the e-commerce platform.

Keywords: *IPRs, E-commerce and types, significance of IP in E-commerce and Elements of E-commerce in Intellectual Property.*

Introduction:

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) is the legal rights which have been given to the inventor or creator for protecting his or her invention or creation for a certain period of time. These legal rights give the special right to the inventor or creator or his assignee for totally utilizing his or her invention or creation for a given period of time. In other words Intellectual Property Rights are the rights given to persons over the creations or inventions of their minds. The well-known IPRs are patents, copyrights, trademarks and trade secrets. In India, seven types of intellectual property rights are in the use like patents, copyrights, trademarks, geographical indications, plant varieties, industrial design and semiconductor integrated circuit layout designs. The main purpose of Intellectual Property Rights Acts is to inspire the creation or invention of a wide variety of intellectual goods. To attain

this, IPRs law gives the rights to the people and businesses for creating certain intellectual goods and information for a stipulated or limited period of time. The IPRs laws allow people to protect their creations, original ideas and information, pictures, and any other intellectual property and prevent the copying from unauthorized agency or people.

Intellectual property is the category of property that consist the creation or invention of intellectual goods. In other words, it is specific type of intellectual or intangible assets which have been created or invented.

Objective:

The object of the present research article is to elaborate the relationship of Intellectual Property Rights and E-Commerce.

Methodology:

Descriptive research method has been applied for the completion of the present research article. The data relating to this research article is gathered from various secondary sources like research articles, research papers, magazines, books and from various websites.

Types of Intellectual Property Rights in India:**1. The Copyrights Act, 1957:**

According to the section 13 of the Act, protection under copyright is obtained for original literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works; cinematograph films; and sound recording'. Interestingly, a copyright protection will be given to computer programmes. Under section 17, clearly stated that, author of the original work shall be the first author of the work and owner of this work shall be the rights to give the license to the third author for the use of their work through the written agreement. The protection shall be provided to any published work dramatic works and artistic works for 60 years in addition to the life of the author. Under section 57, special rights have been given to the original author for the protection of their work. The author has the right to claim the authorship of the work and right to claim the damages even after assigning the work to another person.

2. The Trade Marks Act, 1999:

According to the section 2(zb), "Trade Marks means, a mark representation and distinguish of goods or services one person from those of others." In simple word, a trademark is the protection to the goods or services including shapes, colours, symbols, words etc.

3. The Patents Act, 1970:

It is one of the most important intellectual property right which provides the protection to any new

creation or invention. It is an special rights of the inventor and prevents other people to use their invention illegally and steal the registered patent. It is approved for the term of 20 years from the date of filling application. The new patent is registered only if the invention is unique and original.

4. The Design Act, 2000:

According to the section 2(d) of this Act, design means and includes, "only the features of shape, configuration, pattern, ornaments or composition of lines or colours, applied to any article whether in two dimensional or three dimensional or in both forms, by any industrial process or means, whether manual, mechanical or chemical, separate or combined, which in the finished article appeal to an are judged solely by the eye'. For the registration of industrial design i.e. genuine and original innovation, an application has to be made to the Controller General of Patents, Designs and Trade Marks. After the design registration, the initial protection will be for 10 years and will be extended for a further period of 5 years.

5. The Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999:

In India, many of the goods are extensively popular due to their place of origin. For example, Paithani Saree, Rambandhu Chivada Masala, Kolhapuri Chappal etc. these have the factors specific to the place of origin. For the registration of a goods under GI Act requires to submit the statement of describing how the geographical indication affects to the place of origin of the good regarding the quality, characteristics, and reputation of the good; the class of goods; particulars with regards the appearance of the geographical indication and the map of the territory/area/country where the good has originated. The protection will

be given for the period of 10 years after the geographical indication is awarded and there is option of renovation and extension for the period of 10 more years from the expiry date of original registration.

6. The Protection of Plant Varieties and Farmer's Rights Act, 2001:

The main purpose of this act is to recognize the rights of Indian Farmers and provides the protection to the plant varieties in order to inspire the growth and development of more plant varieties in India. Under this act, the protection shall be given for the period of 9 years in terms of trees and vines and for a period of 6 years in terms of crops with renewal option for these registrations.

7. The Semiconductor Integrated Circuits Layout- Design Act, 2000:

Under this act, the main requirement for registration of a semiconductor integrated circuit should be original layout-designs. The protection is provided to the registered original layout-designs for a period of 10 years.

Types of E-commerce:

E-commerce is doing business through online mode i.e. buying and selling goods through the internet connection. For this, companies will have to create their own websites. E-commerce are classified in to four major categories.

1. Business to Business (B2B):

In business to business, one business purchase or sells their product to/by other business like manufacturer sales product to distributor, and wholesaler sales their product to retailer but not to directly end user i.e. customer.

2. Business to Consumer (B2C):

In business to consumer e-commerce business, business transactions have been made between business and consumer. The products are directly sales to the end user not to the other business.

3. Consumer to Consumer (C2C):

In consumer to consumer business model, two consumers are connected to the online business. It is a business model where individual trade products or services directly each other through the online marketplace. Examp^l, Etsy, eBay, AliExpress which collects sellers with buyers, OLX is classified platform where users can list and sell items like cars, property and electronics.

4. Consumer to Business (C2B):

Consumer to business is a commerce model where consumers provide various products or services to businesses. Through the C2B model, businesses obtain information from their consumers to produce high-quality goods and services. Example, food bloggers sharing a link to a company's cooking products on their blog

Significance of Intellectual Property in E-Commerce:

Intellectual property rights provide the protections against disclosure of trade secrets and unfair competition. Importance of IPR is explained with the help of following points.

1. Safeguarding own creation:

Many of the intellectual property owners give the rights to their creation prior to taking permission for protection of that asset. Intellectual Property Rights provide the protection to the asset creation or invention to intellectual asset owner against the malpractices.

2. Violating intellectual property by others:

Most of the E-commerce websites frequently violate the provisions of Intellectual Property Rights Laws those who selling and buying products through online modes. There are some basics things which must be kept in mind at the rime of trading through online mode:

- a. It must be own creation.

- b. Permission granted by the creator to use.
- c. It must be under the ambit of public domain.
- d. It is covered under fair use.

Elements of E-commerce in Intellectual Property:

The large numbers of constituents are used in e-commerce business. There are numerous parts in e-commerce websites which are conferred the protection of various kinds of Intellectual property.

1. Search engines, e-commerce and other technical tools are admitted to protect under patents.
2. Software is protected under copyrights or patents act depending upon the respective national law.
3. Website of e-commerce business is protected under copyrights act.
4. A website content which includes the written material, graphics, photographs, videos, music etc. is protected under copyrights act.
5. Business name, Logos, Product Names, Domain Names etc. are provided protection in trademarks act.
6. Computer based graphics, displays, and webpages are provided protection under industrial design laws.
7. Secrete elements of website like source code, programs, algorithm, confidential graphics etc. are provided protection in trade law secrets.

Conclusion:

E-commerce is a rapidly growing trading platform where the people can access all the services regarding buying the product and or services. On this platform, various instances can be found regarding the accession of creation and invention of someone without giving any credit to the inventor or creator. So, Intellectual Property Rights plays pivotal role to protect the

contents which are kept in online mode. Several e-commerce businesses act between business and consumers. Because of this purpose, an intellectual property right plays a very important role to make these transactions safer.

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